

Role of Ultrasonography Guided Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) of Hepatic Lesions and Its Histopathological CorrelationAfreen Asgar¹, Chand Prakash Jaiswal², Reena Sinha³, Amod Kumar⁴, Sunil Kumar⁵¹Post-graduate (Trainee), Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Professor, Head of Department, Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India^{3,4,5}Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Amod Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** The liver is the largest internal organ of the body. The present study was carried out to evaluate the diagnostic efficacy of guided FNAC in neoplastic and non-neoplastic focal lesions of the liver.**Materials & methods:** Seventy-two patients admitted to or attending the OPD of Nalanda Medical College and Hospital with suspected hepatic lesions. The present study included a total of 72 fine needle aspirates obtained from patients who visited our pathology department with various space-occupying lesions of the liver. Ultrasonography was done. For histopathological examination, the core needle biopsy was performed concurrently with the FNA under local anaesthesia and ultrasound guidance using the Vim-Silverman liver biopsy needle, wherever possible. The tissue obtained was fixed in 10% formalin and processed. The paraffin sections were stained with routine H & E stains. All the results were recorded in a Microsoft Excel sheet and were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software.**Results:** Cytological diagnosis was neoplastic lesions in 69.56 percent of the patients, while it was non-neoplastic lesions in the remaining 30.43 percent of the patients. Statistical Indices of FNA Diagnosis as calculated by the Galen and Gambino method: Sensitivity: 94.12% Specificity: 80% Positive Predictive Value (PPV): 96.97% Negative Predictive Value (NPV): 66.67% Diagnostic Accuracy: 92.31% Area Under Curve (AUC): 0.871 P value: 0.001 (Significant).**Conclusion:** Guided FNAC is a safe, useful, and economic procedure with virtually no complications and can be routinely done for assisting the diagnosis of liver diseases in our clinical setup. USG/CT guidance offers a better approach to hepatic lesions and avoids injury to vital abdominal structures.**Key words:** FNAC, neoplastic, non-neoplasticThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Liver is the largest internal organ of the body. It provides a suitable medium for growth of neoplastic cells, especially for metastatic tumors because of its size, anatomic location, dual blood supply and ready availability of nutrition [1]. The Fine needle aspiration cytology has proven to be a very effective means of obtaining tissue from many different body sites for diagnosis [2]. This procedure is widely practiced and is a cost-effective and safe method that can be employed to differentiate benign from malignant lesions of the liver [2,3]. The differential diagnosis of hepatic mass lesions includes primary liver tumours, benign or malignant, metastatic deposits, congenital and acquired cysts, abscesses, and granulomas.[4,5] Single or

multiple focal abnormalities demonstrated by palpation or ultrasonography (USG) constitute the main indication for FNAC of the liver [4].

Occasionally, inflammatory lesions or diffuse liver diseases may mimic mass-like lesions or appear as non-homogenous regions on radiographs; such lesions are also sampled by FNA to rule out neoplasms [2]. When FNA provides an early diagnosis, the total number of procedures, especially invasive tests, may be reduced, with a decrease in the length of hospital stay [3]. As there are very few real contraindications and practically no risk of significant complications, guided FNAC of most of the focal hepatic lesions can be performed safely to arrive at an early diagnosis [5]. The relative safety of FNAC

is such that it may be used in very sick patients to obtain information when biopsy carries too high a risk. It is with this view that the present study was carried out to evaluate the diagnostic efficacy of guided FNAC in neoplastic and non-neoplastic focal lesions of the liver. Hence, this observation has been undertaken to study the cytological features of hepatic masses and to correlate with its histological features. This study was conducted at a single tertiary care hospital, NMCH, Patna, Bihar.

Aim and Objectives

The present study is planned with the objective to:

- Evaluate the role of USG-guided percutaneous fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) in the diagnosis of hepatic lesions.
- To correlate FNAC diagnosis with its histopathological features, wherever possible.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

The present study was a prospective observational study and cross-sectional study.

Study Place

This study was conducted at the cytology section of the Department of Pathology in collaboration with Department of Radiology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Study Period

The study was carried out from October 2022 to July 2024.

Study Population

Seventy-two patients of both genders admitted to or attending the OPD of Nalanda Medical College and Hospital with clinically and radiologically diagnosed various space-occupying hepatic lesions were referred for FNAC in the Cytology section of the Department of Pathology, NMCH, Patna, and were included in the study.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the research and ethical committee of the NMCH, Patna.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients to give written informed consent.
- All patients with hepatic lesions confirmed by radiological examination.
- Available for follow-up.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with marked hemorrhagic diathesis.
- Smears with low cellularity.
- Smears obscured by blood, mucus and inflammatory cells.
- The patients diagnosed of having cavernous hemangioma and hydatid disease of liver by USG were excluded to prevent undue complications.
- Uncooperative patients or patients who did not give consent and unable to attend follow-up

Procedure

Detailed clinical data, which include the patient's history, physical examination findings, and reports of relevant investigations, are recorded from the patients who present with clinically and radiologically diagnosed hepatic lesions. After taking consent from the patients, FNAC of the hepatic lesion is done using a 22-gauge lumbar puncture needle with a stylet attached to a 10 ml disposable plastic syringe under USG guidance, taking aseptic precautions. Smears were prepared from the aspirated material, fixed on good-quality, clean, grease-free glass slides in isopropyl alcohol, and stained with haematoxylin and eosin, examined and interpreted by cytopathologists.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained was subjected to statistical analysis using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analysed using software Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 25.0 version. The data were represented in tables and graphs. Categorical variables were summarised in frequency and percent distribution, and a chi-square test was performed by a statistician. A p-value less than 0.05 was deemed significant.

Results

The results of 72 cases with liver lesions have been analysed cytologically in correlation with needle biopsy, wherever possible. Core needle biopsy was available for histopathological examination in 43 cases. A correlation between FNAC and histopathological study was done. The maximum number of lesions was seen in the age group 31-40 years (27.54%) with a mean age of 47.98 years with a standard deviation of 15.61 years. The age of the patients ranged from 24 years to 76 years.

Table 1: Age group wise distribution of patients

Age group (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	08	11.59
31-40	22	30.56
41-50	10	14.49
51-60	14	20.29
61-70	12	17.39
71-80	06	8.69
Total	72	100

Graph 1: Age group wise distribution of patients

Table 1 and graph 1, shows that A total of 72 patients were included in the study in which there were 23 (31.94%) females and 49 (68.06%) males.

Table 2: Categorization of cytologic diagnosis of hepatic lesions

Category	FNAC	Percentage (%)
Non-neoplastic lesion	21	30.43
Neoplastic lesion	48	69.56
Total	69	100

Table 2 shows that Cytological diagnosis was neoplastic lesions in 69.56 percent of the patients while it was non-neoplastic lesions in the remaining 30.43 percent of the patients.

Table 3: Cytologic diagnosis of non-neoplastic lesions

Cytologic diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Pyogenic abscess	13	61.90
Amoebic abscess	4	19.05
Hepatic cyst	2	9.52
Granulomatous hepatitis	2	9.52
Total	21	99.99

Graph 2: Cytologic diagnosis of non-neoplastic lesions

Table 3 and graph 2, shows that In the present study, Pyogenic abscess was seen in 13 (61.90%) cases followed by Amoebic abscess 4 (19.05%), Hepatic cyst 2 (9.52%) and Granulomatous hepatitis 2 (9.52%).

Table 4: Cytologic diagnosis of Neoplastic lesions

Cytologic diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Hepatic adenoma	1	2.08
Hepatocellular carcinoma	17	35.42
Cholangiocarcinoma	1	2.08
Non-Hodgkin’s lymphoma	1	2.08
Poorly diff Carcinoma	4	8.33
Metastatic carcinoma	24	50.00
Total	48	100

Table 4 shows that Metastatic carcinomas were seen in half of the cases about 24 (50.01%) followed by Hepatocellular carcinoma 17 (35.42%), Poorly diff carcinoma 4 (8.33%) and 1 (2.08%) case of Hepatic adenoma, Cholangiocarcinoma and 1 case (2.08%) of non-Hodgkin’s lymphoma.

Table 5: Categorization of Histologic diagnosis of hepatic lesions

Category Histologic	Diagnosis	Percentage (%)
Non-neoplastic	9	20.93
Neoplastic	34	79.06
Total	43	100

Graph 3: Percentage wise categorization of histologic diagnosis of hepatic lesions

Table 5 and graph 3, shows that in the present study, neoplastic lesions were diagnosed histologically in 34 cases (79.06%) followed by non-neoplastic lesions in 9 cases (20.93%).

Table 6: Histologic diagnosis of Non-Neoplastic lesions

Histologic diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Pyogenic abscess	6	66.67
Amoebic abscess	1	11.11
Hepatic cyst	1	11.11
Granulomatous hepatitis	1	11.11
Total	9	100

Table 6 shows that In the present study Pyogenic abscess were seen in 6 (66.67%) and Amoebic abscess, Hepatic cyst and Granulomatous hepatitis were seen in 1 (11.11%) case.

Table 7: Histologic diagnosis of Neoplastic lesions

Histologic diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Hepatic adenoma	0	0
Hepatocellular carcinoma	13	38.24
Cholangiocarcinoma	1	2.94
Poorly diff carcinoma	1	2.94
Metastatic carcinoma	19	55.88
Total	34	100

Table 7 shows that metastatic carcinomas were seen in half of the cases about 19 (55.88%) followed by Hepatocellular carcinoma 12 (35.30%), Poorly diff carcinoma 2 (5.88%) and Cholangiocarcinoma 1 (2.94%) and no case of Hepatic adenoma was found.

Table 8: Correlation of Cytologic diagnosis and Histologic diagnosis of Neoplastic lesion

Cytologic diagnosis	Histologic diagnosis	
	Neoplastic	Non-Neoplastic
Neoplastic	TP=34	FP=1
Non-Neoplastic	TP=2	FP=6

Statistical Indices of FNA Diagnosis as calculated by Galen and Gambino method: Sensitivity: 94.12% Specificity: 80% Positive Predictive Value (PPV): 96.97% Negative Predictive Value (NPV): 66.67% Diagnostic Accuracy: 92.31% Area Under Curve (AUC): 0.871 P value: 0.001 (Significant).

Graph 4: ROC Curve for Neoplastic lesion

Discussion

Fine needle aspiration cytology has proven to be a very effective means of obtaining tissue from many different body sites for diagnosis. Nowadays, this procedure is widely practiced and is a cost-effective and safe method that can be employed to differentiate benign from malignant processes [6]. In this study, guided FNAC was performed in 72 patients with hepatic lesions. There were 47 (68.12%) males and 25 (31.88%) females. The age range of the patients was 21 to 80 years. Samples were adequate in 69 patients (95.83%). FNAC yielded inadequate samples in three (4.16%) patients. This is comparable to those reported by Gathphoh et al. [7], was 2.5% and Talukdar et al. [8], was 6.5%. Of 69 patients, 48 (70.15%) cases were interpreted as neoplastic lesions and 21 (29.85%) cases as non-neoplastic lesions. Among neoplastic lesions, metastatic deposits were the commonest (50.01%). This is inconsistent with observations made by Gathphoh et al. [7], in 2003 and Talukdar et al. [8], in 2004. Primary malignancies of the liver were diagnosed in 18 cases, of which 17 were hepatocellular carcinomas. The remaining 1 case was of cholangiocarcinoma. Of 21 non-neoplastic lesions diagnosed on guided FNAC, 19 were inflammatory lesions, including 13 cases of pyogenic abscesses, 4 of amoebic abscesses, and 2 of granulomatous hepatitis. 2 cases were of benign cystic lesions.

Although imaging techniques have helped greatly with the early and correct diagnosis of liver abscess, the appearances are often non-specific.[9] There is some overlap between the radiological features of liver abscesses, HCC, and metastases. Two situations may occur: (1) tumour masses, whether primary or secondary, undergo extensive necrosis, with the resultant radiologic image of the cavitary neoplasms mimicking abscesses; (2) abscesses are accompanied by proliferative reactive

changes, making radiologic differentiation from a neoplastic process almost impossible. In those cases, fine needle aspiration biopsy plays an essential complementary role [9]. In our study, 10 cases of pyogenic liver abscesses, the smears showed plenty of neutrophils and nuclear debris along with few degenerating hepatocytes. Histopathology was available in 6 patients, in which 4 confirmed the cytological diagnosis. The changes were similar to findings described by Wee et al. [9]. Problems in diagnosis arise when overt manifestations of infections are absent. This difficulty is compounded by the fact that other hepatic conditions, such as malignant neoplasms, primary or secondary, can be multifocal and undergo tumour necrosis and present with an associated fever, simulating abscess [9]. This resulted in two false negative results in our study, which on histopathology was confirmed as metastatic adenocarcinoma. In our 4 cases of amoebic liver abscess, the smear showed necrotic cellular debris, degenerating hepatocytes, and mixed inflammatory cells. The characteristic feature was the presence of trophozoites of *E. histolytica* in MGG-stained cytosmears. In Wee et al. [9] study, the smears lacked neutrophils but showed copious granular debris and necrotic cells with ghost outlines, including necrotic hepatocytes. Roy et al. [10], also diagnosed amoebic abscess in 5 of 9 cases of liver abscess by the presence of anti-amoebic antibodies in the serum. There were 2 cases diagnosed as granulomatous hepatitis in the present study (2.77%) in which cytosmears showed epithelioid histiocytes in singles and small clusters along with multinucleated giant cells and few benign hepatocytes with the presence of caseous necrotic material. Histopathological correlation was available in only one case in our study. Granulomatous hepatitis is reported rarely [11]. The diagnostic value of cytological findings indicative of granulomatous diseases of the liver may be of variable

clinical value and significance since granulomas are found in a wide variety of causes, such as chronic infections (e.g., tuberculosis), drugs, foreign bodies, neoplasms, and lymphomas. Thus, cytologic finding of a granuloma in a liver aspirate needs to be correlated clinically [11].

Fine needle aspiration of the liver is commonly used for diagnosing hepatic malignancies, primary or metastatic [12, 13]. We encountered 48 (70.15%) neoplastic lesions out of 69 cases. 18 cases (37.5%) were primary tumours, and 24 cases (50.01%) were metastatic tumours, one case of hepatic adenoma, one case of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, and four cases of poorly differentiated carcinoma. The majority were metastatic adenocarcinoma (50.01%), followed by HCCs (35.42%). 17 cases (35.42%) of HCC were diagnosed on cytologic examination. Most of the patients were 14 males, with 3 females. Male-to-female ratio of 3.5:1 and was comparable to those observed by Wee et al. (2.53:1) [14]. More frequency of HCC in males may partly be due to the higher carrier rate of hepatitis B in males [15]. One case was reported as well-differentiated hepatocellular carcinoma, which came out to be hepatic adenoma on histopathology. Metastatic lesions constituted 50.01% of all hepatic malignancies in our study, which is lower than the frequencies reported by Pinto et al. [15], (89%) and Das et al. 16 (65.6%). The primary site was found to be the colon in 4 of the cases and the rectum in 2 cases. We had one case of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. The aspirate smears were hypercellular and showed diffuse monomorphic atypical lymphoid cells. The cells had scant cytoplasm with clumped chromatin and prominent nucleoli. Background showed lymphoglandular bodies and hepatocytes. Cytological features were similar to those described by Kuo et al. [16], who observed 4 cases (0.76%). With an accuracy of 92.31% for liver lesions, fine needle aspiration of hepatic lesions is a valuable method that allows rapid diagnosis. However, its sensitivity depends on the site and depth of the lesion and the skill of the person who performs the fine needle aspiration.

Limitations of study and USG-guided FNAC

A more accurate result could be obtained with a larger number of participants and a multicentric study. The only absolute contraindication for the procedure is uncorrectable severe coagulopathy.

Conclusion

Guided FNAC is a safe, useful and economic procedure with virtually no complications and can be routinely done for assisting the diagnosis of liver diseases in our clinical set up. USG/CT guidance offers a better approach to hepatic lesions and avoids injury to vital abdominal structures. Guided FNAC shows a very high diagnostic yield. The technique can be safely repeated if the amount of aspirate is inadequate, or diagnosis is inconclusive to reach a 100% adequate sampling. Under

USG/CT guidance, it is a sensitive and specific technique for diagnosis of deep-seated lesions. This diagnostic method can be used to identify the vast majority of neoplasms of primary or metastatic nature. Considering the overall advantages and cost analysis, FNAC under imaging guidance can be suggested as the initial method of choice for evaluation of hepatic lesions in most clinical settings.

Acknowledgement

We appreciate our patients' cooperation and participation in this study. The authors would like to acknowledge the entire faculties and staff of the Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India, for their valuable support and time-to-time suggestions in undertaking the present study. Special thanks to Dr. Chand Prakash Jaiswal, Professor and Head of Department, Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India, for their valuable suggestions during the study

References

1. Svante R Orell et al. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology, Churchill Livingstone, 5th edition, 2011, p293
2. Das DK, Tripathi RP, Chachra KL, Sodhani P, Parkash S, Bhambhani S. Role of guided fine needle aspiration cytology in diagnosis and classification of liver malignancies. *Tropical Gastroenterology* 1997; 18:101-106.
3. Tsui WM, Cheng F, Lee Y. Fine needle aspiration cytology of liver tumours. *Annual of Contemporary Diagnostic Pathology* 1998; Volume 2:79-93.
4. Geller SA, Pitman MB. Morphological diagnostic procedures (liver biopsy). In: MacSween RNM, Burt AD, Portman BC, Ishak KG, Scheuer PJ, Anthony PP, eds. *Pathology of Liver*. 4 th ed. London: Churchill Livingstone; 2002:943-960
5. Leiman G. Liver and Spleen. In; Orell SR, Sterret GF, Whitaker D, eds. *Fine needle aspiration cytology*. 4 th Ed. New Delhi: Churchill Livingstone; 2005:293-316
6. Hajdu SI, D'Ambrosio FG, Fields V, Lightdale CJ. Aspiration and brush cytology of the liver. *Semin diag Pathol* 1986; 3: 227-238.
7. Gathphoh ED, Gaytri S, Babina S, Singh AM. Fine needle aspiration cytology of liver: A study of 202 cases. *Ind J Med Sci* 2003; 57:22-25
8. Talukder SI, Huq MH, Haque MA, Rahman S, Islam SM, Hossain GA, et al. Ultrasound guided fine needle aspiration cytology for diagnosis of mass lesions of liver. *Mymensingh Med J* 2004; 13:25-29.
9. Wee A, Nilsson B, Yap I, Chong SM. Aspiration cytology of liver abscess-with an emphasis on diagnostic pitfalls. *Acta cytol* 1995; 39:453-462.

10. Roy M, Bhattacharyya A, Dasgupta S, Sanyal S. Fallacies of fine needle aspiration cytology surgical lesion of the liver. *J Indian Med Assoc* 1994;92(9):285-287.
11. Radhika S, Rajawanshi A, Kochhar R, Kochhar S, Dey P, Roy P. Abdominal Tuberculosis-Diagnosis by fine needle aspiration cytology. *Acta Cytol* 1993; 37:673-678.
12. Kung ITM, Chan SKC, Fung KH. Fine needle aspiration in hepatocellular carcinoma- combined cytologic and histologic approach. *Cancer* 1991; 67:673-680.
13. Bottles K, Cohen MB, Holly EA, Chiu SH, Abele JS, Cello JP, et al. A step-wise logistic regression analysis of hepatocellular carcinoma- An aspiration biopsy study. *Cancer* 1988;62:558-563
14. Wee A, Nilsson B, Tan LKA, Yap I. Fine needle aspiration biopsy of hepatocellular carcinoma-Diagnostic dilemma at the ends of the spectrum. *Acta Cytol* 1994; 38:347-354.
15. Sautereau D, Vire O, Cazes PY, Cazals JB, Catanzano G, Claude R, et al. Value of sonographically guided fine needle aspiration biopsy in evaluating the liver with sonographic abnormalities. *Gastroenterology* 1987; 93:715-718.
16. Das DK, Tripathi RP, Chachra KL, Sodhani P, Parkash S, Bhambhani S. Role of guided fine needle aspiration cytology in diagnosis and classification of liver malignancies. *Tropical Gastroenterology* 1997; 18:101-106